

Matching Researchers to Funding Calls: A Reproducible Institution-Level Framework

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Abstract

Grant recommendation systems remain one of the least explored areas within academic recommender systems, and existing proposals are typically tied to specific funding agencies or disciplinary domains. This paper presents an institution-level reproducible framework for matching researchers to funding opportunities by combining bibliometric profiling with semantic matching. Rather than representing each researcher through a single aggregated profile, the framework constructs multiple publication sets defined by bibliometric criteria such as authorship position and time window, each independently compared against funding calls using word embeddings. Within-researcher normalisation and percentile-based ranking transform cosine similarity scores into actionable recommendations. A case study applied to 3,013 researchers from the University of Granada and 291 Horizon Europe topics verify it and shows that the four indicators capture complementary signals.

Keywords

Research funding; Grant recommendation; Bibliometric profiling; Semantic matching; SPECTER2; Horizon Europe; Scopus

Contributorship statement

WAM - Conceptualization; Investigation; Methodology; Project administration; Supervision; Visualization; Writing - Original Draft; Writing - Review & Editing.

LLS - Data Curation; Formal analysis; Investigation; Software; Writing - Original Draft.

COS - Data Curation; Formal analysis; Investigation; Software; Writing - Original Draft.

EdlFG - Funding acquisition; Project administration; Resources.

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44 **1. Introduction**

45 Science is not free. Research requires financial resources that go beyond institutional budgets,
46 making external funding an essential component of academic activity (Thelwall et al., 2023).
47 Despite the undeniable societal benefits of scientific investment, quantifying and
48 communicating these returns in terms that the general public can readily understand remains a
49 considerable challenge (Lane, 2009; Yin et al., 2022). Nevertheless, its direct impact and
50 implications within the scientific realm is more tangible. Funding does not merely make
51 scientific progress possible, but it also enhances research outputs, though its effect depends on
52 the diversity of funding sources and rarely shows in the short term (Ding & Bu, 2025; Gök et
53 al., 2016). Moreover, and beyond productivity, external funding also influences academic
54 relationships, by raising international collaborations (Ubfal & Maffioli, 2011). However,
55 despite such benefits, this dependence on external support is not without its complications.
56 Securing and managing funding imposes significant administrative and bureaucratic demands
57 on researchers. The rise in pressure to maintain financial continuity can gradually shift attention
58 away from scientific inquiry itself and towards the perpetual pursuit of the next grant
59 (Ioannidis, 2012).

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61 Research funding comes from a multiplicity of actors operating at different levels and driven
62 by their own rationales and interests (Buckley, 2022; Røttingen et al., 2013). Rather than a
63 blank cheque, such funding comes with predefined thematic priorities that researchers must
64 meet, or adapt to, in order to apply for successfully ('Don't Deprioritize Curiosity-Driven
65 Research', 2026). This dependency on external criteria is not without consequences. At its most
66 extreme, this can give rise to active conflicts of interest, as illustrated by the controversy
67 surrounding the science of consciousness (IIT-Concerned et al., 2023). More pervasively, it
68 contributes to a structural misalignment between investment priorities and actual needs (Kumar
69 et al., 2024; Yegros-Yegros et al., 2020). Despite these risks, the funding landscape is broad
70 and diverse enough that researchers will rarely struggle to find opportunities aligned with their
71 interests. The challenge, however, has become navigating an increasingly competitive
72 environment. In this sense, success rates for some European calls have fallen to single-digit
73 figures (Naddaf, 2025), dropped from 26% to 19% for early-stage investigators at the NIH
74 (Kaiser, 2026), and similarly declined in China following a surge in applications (Conroy,
75 2024). Keeping pace with this evolving landscape is a growing challenge, and success in
76 research funding depends heavily on the active pursuit of opportunities (Bol et al., 2018).

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78 From a scientometric perspective, the dynamics and implications of research funding constitute
79 one of the field's recurring topics of inquiry, with acknowledgements in scholarly publications
80 serving as the primary data source for its analysis (Álvarez-Bornstein & Montesi, 2021). Within
81 this framework, several fronts of research have been developed. Efforts have been made to map
82 funding thematically, either to characterise the portfolio of a specific agency (Belter, 2013) or
83 to describe the global funding landscape within a particular field, such as oncology (Schmutz
84 et al., 2019). Alongside this, frameworks have been proposed to account for the structural
85 complexity of funding systems, recognising the multilevel and heterogeneous nature with
86 which researchers combine funding sources in practice (Aagaard et al., 2021). Inequalities in
87 funding access have also been documented, with biases linked to researchers' gender (Bol et
88 al., 2022), institutional size and prestige (Murray et al., 2016), and research area (Tian et al.,
89 2024). Equally, it has been examined the impact of funding on scientific output (Jacob &
90 Lefgren, 2011), on academic careers (Bloch et al., 2014), and on the monitoring and evaluation
91 mechanisms that funders themselves apply to the research they support (Abudu et al., 2022).
92 However, most of these studies are descriptive and explanatory in nature, with little bearing on
93 the application process itself.

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One of the most direct and forward-looking applications has been the development of funding recommendation systems. However, grant recommender systems represent one of the least explored areas within academic recommender systems (Z. Zhang et al., 2023). Finding relevant funding in large databases is a difficult and time-consuming process for most researchers, and the commercial tools available offer very limited search capabilities (Zhu et al., 2023). Early systems addressed this problem through keywords and association rules (Kamada et al., 2015, 2016), whilst later proposals incorporated information retrieval techniques such as TF-IDF or BM25 (Acuna et al., 2022). More recent developments have incorporated language models such as BERT (Devlin et al., 2018), or specialised biomedical embeddings such as BioWordVec (Y. Zhang et al., 2019) and BioSentVec (Chen et al., 2019). However, despite this progress, most of these proposals share a structural limitation. They are *ad hoc* solutions, developed for specific domains, institutions, or funding sources, with limited capacity for generalisation and difficult to transfer to other contexts. Moreover, their bibliometric approach relies solely on metadata fields such as titles and abstracts to construct the semantic connection.

No grant recommendation system to date offers a scalable solution across different institutions that fully exploits bibliometric data. This paper addresses that gap by proposing a method for aligning research funding opportunities with researcher profiles through the combination of bibliometric and semantic techniques. This approach aims to support research institutions at two complementary levels. At the individual level, it alerts researchers to the funding opportunities most aligned with their profile, reducing the effort and uncertainty involved in funding searches. At the institutional level, it enables research offices to identify, for each call, the most suitable candidate within their community, providing a basis for the strategic allocation of research expertise across funding opportunities. The specific objectives are:

1. To design a methodological framework that integrates bibliometric indicators and semantic methods to measure the alignment between research funding calls and researcher profiles.
2. To validate the framework through a case study drawing on researcher profiles from the University of Granada (UGR) and *Horizon Europe* topics, using *Scopus* as the primary bibliographic data source.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the proposed methodological framework, outlining its theoretical foundations and core components. Section 3 details the case study, including the methodology adopted, the data collected, and the indicators employed. Section 4 presents the results obtained from the case study application. Section 5 discusses the findings and examines the limitations of the framework. Finally, Section 6 draws the conclusions of this work.

2. Methodological framework

The methodological framework is presented below and summarised in **Figure 1**. The workflow is organised into three main blocks: (1) database generation, comprising bibliographic and authorship data alongside calls for proposals; (2) multidimensional researcher profiling, which prepares both researcher and call data for subsequent comparison and matching; and (3) scoring and ranking, which compares and identifies the most relevant funding opportunities for each researcher. It should be noted that, as a methodological framework, it is not designed to be bound to a specific dataset, context, or configuration, but to remain adaptable across multiple scenarios. Also, it is conceived to support research institutions in monitoring funding opportunities and aligning them with their researchers' profiles, with part of its potential residing in its ability to discriminate and identify the most suitable researchers within the

144 institution. The case study, described subsequently, specifies a concrete setting and details the
 145 technical implementation of the framework in practice.

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147 **Figure 1.** Methodological framework for matching researchers to funding opportunities.

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150 2.1. Database generation

151 2.1.1. Data extraction

152 The first step is the construction of the database, which draws on at least two independent
 153 sources. On one hand, a bibliographic source providing publication records and authorship
 154 data, together comprising sufficient metadata to support basic bibliometric operations. On the
 155 other, a funding source providing basic information on the calls for proposals.

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157 The bibliographic source may consist of a single database or a combination of several, to obtain
 158 broader coverage and a more comprehensive understanding of the institution's research output.
 159 This may be particularly relevant for institutions with a more multidisciplinary profile or whose
 160 publications are not exclusively oriented towards international journals, for which databases
 161 such as *Web of Science* or *Scopus* may offer biased coverage (Asubiaro et al., 2024;
 162 Gusenbauer, 2024). Where available, a Current Research Information System (CRIS) may
 163 itself serve as the primary source, as it is specifically designed to capture the full scope of an
 164 institution's research activity and typically holds normalised researcher records alongside
 165 production tracked across multiple sources. In any case, the selected source or combination of
 166 sources must meet a set of minimum requirements:

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1. It must provide coverage that is sufficiently representative of the institution's output over a minimum period to constitute a reliable baseline.
2. Since it will underpin the semantic matching process, it is necessary to ensure that as many publications as possible include, in addition to the title, an abstract; a publication lacking this will not be excluded but will be processed with less information. This is a pertinent consideration when selecting a source, as some publishers have ceased to make abstracts openly available, thereby affecting open sources such as *Crossref* and *OpenAlex* ('Publishers Close Access to Scholarly Content Such as Abstracts Due to AI Incentives', 2025). The presence of keywords or topics (e.g., *OpenAlex* topic classification) enriches the representation when available, but their absence does not compromise the process in the same way.
3. The source must include some mechanism for author identification, whether a persistent identifier (e.g., *ORCID*, *Web of Science ResearcherID*, *Scopus Author ID*...), email

180 address, or a normalised name, to facilitate the unambiguous aggregation of each
181 researcher's output and to verify that the works assigned to a given individual genuinely
182 belong to them.

- 183 4. The source must provide the metadata fields required by the bibliometric criteria to be
184 applied. For instance, if the framework is configured to filter by publication year or
185 authorship position, the source must include reliable information for those fields.

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187 The funding source, for its part, provides the counterpart to the bibliographic data, with less
188 demanding requirements. Just as publications require a title, abstract and keywords for
189 embedding vectorisation, analogous information is needed here. Apart from the title, calls for
190 proposals do not typically include a summary that meets the formal characteristics of a
191 scientific abstract. However, they must offer details on the thematic scope, lines of work or
192 expected outcomes that serve this purpose and allow the focus of the call to be properly
193 understood. Keywords may likewise appear in the form of a controlled thesaurus or a thematic
194 classification (e.g., MeSH, EuroSciVoc, UNESCO codes). The aim is to construct, from the
195 available information, a document structurally analogous to a scientific publication, as
196 summarised in **Table 1**. Ultimately, both publications and calls must be representable through
197 the same set of textual fields, even if their nature and form differ, sharing ultimately a common
198 academic language.

199
200 **Table 1.** Field equivalence between publications and calls for proposals.

Field	Publications	Calls	Description
<i>Title*</i>	Title	Title	Concise identifier of the document's subject matter
<i>Abstract</i>	Abstract	Description Destination Expected outcome Scope	Core textual field for semantic vectorisation
<i>Keywords</i>	Keywords Topics	Keywords Category Classification Thesaurus	Controlled or free-text terms that reinforce the thematic signal

201 *Mandatory in both cases as the minimum unit of semantic content

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203 *2.1.2. Researcher data normalization*

204 Of the two sources described above, the bibliographic one(s) requires a processing step before
205 any further analysis can be carried out. A single researcher may appear under multiple profiles
206 in a bibliographic database, and correctly merging and assigning their publications is the
207 foundation for the bibliometric layer of the framework, from which their multidimensional
208 profile will subsequently be constructed. This process is facilitated when the source provides
209 information such as *ORCID*, email addresses, or institutional affiliations. Regardless of the
210 database used, this step is always necessary, although the effort involved will vary depending
211 on the quality and normalisation of the source data (Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2024).
212 However, as noted above, where a CRIS serves as the primary source, this step is considerably
213 simplified, as researcher profiles are typically already resolved.

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215 **2.2. Multidimensional researcher profiling**

216 *2.2.1. Bibliometric profiling*

217 Prior approaches to researcher-grant matching typically represent researchers through
218 aggregated profiles or researcher-defined keyword queries (Z. Zhang et al., 2024; Zhu et al.,
219 2023), or cluster publications into thematic groups before comparison (Zhu et al., 2023). The
220 present framework departs from this logic. Rather than treating the researcher as a single entity,
221 it constructs multiple publication sets per researcher, each defined by a specific bibliometric
222 criterion that isolates a distinct signal about their role, interests or thematic orientation. Each
223 set is compared independently against the call, producing not a single score but a set of
224 indicators that together profile the researcher's alignment, closer to a dashboard than to a
225 summary measure.

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227 The criteria used to define these sets can vary depending on analytical goals and available data.
228 Authorship position is one option, as first, last or corresponding authorship conventionally
229 signals a more central intellectual contribution or leadership role (Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al.,
230 2019; Rennie, 2000). Others might include publications above a given impact threshold, works
231 involving international collaboration, or output within a specific subfield. Each criterion
232 isolates a subset of the researcher's output that constitutes interpretable evidence about their
233 expertise and interests. To ensure scores rest on a sufficient empirical base, minimum
234 publication thresholds are applied. As a result, researchers who do not meet the threshold for a
235 given set are excluded from that ranking but may still appear in others.

236
237 The time frame operates as a cross-cutting dimension that can be applied in combination with
238 any of the criteria above. Rather than defining a different type of publication, it modulates the
239 time window over which each set is constructed, so that the same criterion can be applied over
240 a medium-term horizon or over a shorter window, which is more sensitive to recent shifts in
241 focus or the emergence of new research lines. Combining both horizons with each criterion
242 allows the framework to distinguish between what a researcher has worked on and what they
243 are working on now, a distinction that is particularly relevant when the goal is to identify
244 candidates with both depth of expertise and current engagement with a given topic.

245
246 Furthermore, defining publication sets prior to vectorisation also offers a computational
247 advantage, as only the publications belonging to a given set need to be encoded. Publications
248 that do not meet any criterion are not vectorised at all, reducing the overall computational cost.

249 *2.2.2. Semantic matching*

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251 Early grant recommendation systems relied exclusively on lexical representations, such as
252 keyword matching and association rules (Kamada et al., 2015, 2016), which assume shared
253 vocabulary between researchers and calls. As computational capacity and machine learning
254 techniques advanced, more sophisticated approaches emerged, with word embeddings now
255 outperforming these lexical methods in grant recommendation tasks (Z. Zhang et al., 2024; Zhu
256 et al., 2023). Each publication within a publication set, alongside the call, is transformed into
257 such a vector using the textual fields described in Section 2.1.1. (title, abstract and keywords
258 where available, and their equivalent for funding calls). This vectorisation is performed at the
259 individual publication level, rather than at the level of an aggregated researcher profile, which
260 is precisely the operation for which these specific pre-trained models are designed and at which
261 they perform most reliably.

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263 Although general-purpose language models can be applied, the vocabulary, syntax and
 264 semantic conventions of academic publications differ substantially from general text, and
 265 models trained on broad corpora tend to underperform when applied to domain-specific
 266 matching tasks (Fahrudin et al., 2025; Wolff et al., 2024). Specialised models encode the way
 267 in which scientific concepts relate to one another, producing more coherent and discriminating
 268 similarity scores when comparing publications to funding calls. This advantage is especially
 269 relevant for multidisciplinary institutions, where the thematic breadth of the research portfolio
 270 requires a model capable of representing diverse scientific domains with comparable fidelity.
 271 Beyond model selection, further refinement is possible through preprocessing and
 272 representation strategies, such as text normalization and field-level weighting, which can
 273 improve the discriminatory power of the resulting vectors.
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275 There are several embedding models for scientific text representation. **Table 2** summarises the
 276 most widely discussed options, all trained on academic corpora and therefore suitable
 277 candidates for this type of application. Empirical comparisons across classification and
 278 similarity tasks consistently show that models pre-trained on scientific literature outperform
 279 general-purpose alternatives, with *SPECTER2* and *SciBERT* emerging as the most robust
 280 options across disciplines (Fahrudin et al., 2025; Wolff et al., 2024). Domain-specific models
 281 such as *BioSentVec* or *BioWordVec* may offer additional precision in institutions with a
 282 predominantly biomedical focus (Z. Zhang et al., 2024; Zhu et al., 2023), though their
 283 advantage tends to diminish outside that domain. The choice of model should therefore be
 284 guided by the disciplinary profile of the institution and the coverage of the available training
 285 corpus relative to its research output.
 286

287 **Table 2.** Main pre-trained word embedding models for academic text.

Model	Training corpus	Base model	Model type	Research areas
<i>SPECTER2</i> (Singh et al., 2022)	~6M citation triplets	SciBERT	Transformer	Multidisciplinary
<i>SciNCL</i> (Ostendorff et al., 2022)	S2ORC	BERT	Transformer	Multidisciplinary
<i>SciBERT</i> (Beltagy et al., 2019)	Semantic Scholar	BERT	Transformer	Biomedical and computer science
<i>BioSentVec</i> (Chen et al., 2019)	PubMed + MIMIC-III clinical notes	—	sent2vec	Biomedical science
<i>BioWordVec</i> (Y. Zhang et al., 2019)	PubMed + MeSH	—	fastText	Biomedical science

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2.3. Scoring and ranking

With publication and call vectors in place, the next step is to quantify their semantic proximity. This is done using cosine similarity, which measures the angle between two vectors in the embedding space and is independent of document length:

$$\text{sim}(p, c) = \frac{\vec{p} \cdot \vec{c}}{|\vec{p}| \cdot |\vec{c}|}$$

where \vec{p} and \vec{c} represent the embedding vectors of a publication and a call respectively, and the resulting score ranges from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating greater semantic proximity.

Once cosine similarity scores have been computed for each publication-call pair within a given publication set, these scores must be aggregated into a single value per researcher and set. The default aggregation is the arithmetic mean of all similarity scores in the set, which provides a balanced estimate of the overall thematic alignment between a researcher's output and the call. However, when a researcher has a large and thematically diverse number of publication records, the mean can be pulled downwards by works that are only loosely related to the call. In such cases, the aggregation is performed over the top 33% of publications by similarity score, capturing the most aligned third of the researcher's output and providing a more discriminating estimate of their peak thematic relevance.

After that, and prior to ranking, each researcher's aggregated similarity scores are standardised using a z-score transformation applied across all their publication-call pairs within a given set. This normalisation step rescales individual scores relative to each researcher's own distribution, rather than across the full population. As a result, researchers whose publication sets span a broad range of themes receive lower effective scores on any single call, whilst those with a more focused profile are rewarded for their thematic concentration. The z-score is computed as:

$$z_{s,r} = \frac{a_{s,r} - \mu_r}{\sigma_r}$$

where $a_{s,r}$ is the aggregated similarity score of researcher r for publication set s , and μ_r and σ_r are the mean and standard deviation of all aggregated scores for that researcher across all publication sets.

The aggregated and normalised score is a continuous value that, taken in isolation, lacks direct interpretability. A score for a given researcher on a given call carries little meaning without knowing whether it is high or low relative to the rest of the community. The framework therefore positions each researcher's score within the distribution of scores obtained by all researchers in the institution for that same call and publication set. This relative positioning is expressed as a percentile rank, so that researchers in the upper percentiles of the distribution are identified as the most promising candidates for a given call. This step transforms an abstract score into an actionable recommendation, grounded in the comparative performance of the full research community rather than in any absolute threshold. Beyond individual recommendations, ranking researchers relative to their own community transforms the framework into an instrument of institutional strategy, as for each call, it identifies the best available match within the institution, naturally distributing visibility across different research profiles.

339 3. Case study

340 3.1. Data and sources

341 The framework was implemented and evaluated using the University of Granada (UGR) as a
342 case study, one of the largest public research universities in Spain, with over 5,487 researchers
343 affiliated across 123 departments at the time of analysis in January 2026¹. The primary
344 bibliographic source was *Scopus*, supplemented by *OpenAlex* for thematic enrichment. In this
345 case study, the availability of the UGR's Current Research Information System (CRIS)²
346 provided a curated master list containing each researcher's verified *Scopus* identifier, *ORCID*
347 iD and institutional email address. Researchers present in *Scopus* but absent from the CRIS
348 were excluded from the study population. This made the CRIS the reference for population
349 definition and enabled the detection and merging of fragmented *Scopus* author profiles.

350
351 Bibliographic data were retrieved from *Scopus* through a two-stage process. In the first stage,
352 all UGR-affiliated records (limited to article, review, letter, book and book chapter) from the
353 last five years (2021-2025) were downloaded via both a manual export and the *Scopus* API.
354 The manual export was necessary to capture the correspondence address field with the email,
355 which the API does not provide due to privacy reasons. This allowed the framework to pair
356 corresponding author email addresses with their *Scopus* Author IDs, with an additional
357 verification step to ensure the email was assigned by *Scopus* to the correct author. The API
358 download served to retrieve full publication metadata and author-level information. Author
359 records were then unified with the CRIS data through a cascading matching procedure applied
360 sequentially by *Scopus* Author ID, *ORCID*, email address and, as a last resort, normalised name
361 string. Where two records shared the same verified name and at least one email address, they
362 were merged into a single profile, consolidating all associated information.

363
364 In the second stage, once the author database had been consolidated, the *Scopus* API was
365 queried again using each researcher's verified *Scopus* Author ID to retrieve all their
366 publications from the study period, regardless of institutional affiliation. This step ensured that
367 output produced prior to or outside the UGR was also captured. The resulting bibliographic
368 database comprised 30,077 publications and 3,759 *Scopus* author profiles, corresponding to
369 3,013 researchers registered in the CRIS with at least three publications. This minimum defines
370 the potential population for analysis, regardless of any additional filters applied subsequently,
371 and represents 55% of the total institutional population. Thematic enrichment was carried out
372 via the *OpenAlex* API, from which the primary topic was retrieved for each publication by DOI.

373
374 The call dataset consisted of 291 *Horizon Europe* topics (hereafter referred to as calls) scraped
375 from the *European Commission's Funding and Tenders Portal*³, covering all six clusters open
376 as of September 2025. For each call, the title and topic description were extracted and combined
377 to construct a document equivalent in structure to a scientific abstract

378
379 **3.2. Data processing and methods**

380 Researcher-call alignment was assessed through four indicators, constructed by crossing two
381 temporal windows with two publication set criteria and summarised in **Table 3**. The temporal
382 dimension distinguishes between a five-year horizon, which captures consolidated thematic
383 expertise, and a two-year window, which is more sensitive to recent shifts in research focus.
384 The rationale is that a researcher may have broadened or redirected their agenda over time, and

¹ <https://produccioncientifica.ugr.es/grupos>

² <https://produccioncientifica.ugr.es/>

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/>

385 recent output is not always representative of their full track record, nor vice versa. The
 386 publication set dimension distinguishes between a researcher's full output and a subset
 387 restricted to first, last or corresponding author positions, which conventionally signals a more
 388 central intellectual contribution, separating works the researcher has actively led from those
 389 where their role was more peripheral. Together, the four indicators offer complementary rather
 390 than redundant signals, allowing the framework to distinguish between depth of expertise and
 391 current engagement.

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Table 3. Multidimensional indicators used to assess researcher-call alignment.

Indicator	Description	Publication set	Time window	Threshold
<i>Research background</i>	Measures the researcher's consolidated thematic alignment with the call	All publications	5 years	≥ 5 publications
<i>Current focus</i>	Captures the researcher's recent thematic orientation	All publications	2 years	≥ 3 publications
<i>Research leadership</i>	Reflects thematic alignment based solely on publications where the researcher led the research	First, last or corresponding author only	5 years	≥ 4 publications
<i>Current leadership</i>	Identifies researchers whose most recent output, restricted to publications where they led the research, aligns with the call	First, last or corresponding author only	2 years	≥ 2 publications

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395 Minimum publication thresholds were defined heuristically through iterative testing. Initial
 396 values were evaluated by inspecting borderline cases at both extremes, that is, thresholds set
 397 too high excluded researchers with relevant profiles but a limited number of publications, while
 398 thresholds set too low admitted profiles with insufficient empirical basis or tangential
 399 relationship. Manual inspection of these edge cases was instrumental in calibrating the final
 400 values. For the *Research background* and *Current focus* sets, the minimum required output is
 401 five and three publications respectively. For the *Research leadership* and *Current Leadership*
 402 sets, the thresholds are four and two publications. Researchers who do not meet the threshold
 403 for a given set are excluded from the corresponding ranking but may still appear in others. It
 404 should be noted that these thresholds do not constitute a universal recommendation. They
 405 represent a pragmatic calibration decision for the specific case study presented here, and their
 406 appropriateness will vary with the size and characteristics of the research community under
 407 analysis. Conceptually, a threshold of this kind could even be operationalised as a soft
 408 boundary, applying a penalty or weight reduction to researchers whose publication count falls
 409 just below the cut-off, rather than enforcing a strict binary exclusion.

410

411 All publications and calls were vectorised using *SPECTER2*, selected on the basis of its
 412 consistent performance across disciplines in prior benchmarking studies (Wolff et al., 2024). It
 413 is important to note that cosine similarity scores produced by *SPECTER2* tend to cluster at high
 414 values⁴, reducing the ability to discriminate between more and less relevant matches (Dhakal
 415 et al., 2025). To address this, a common-component removal procedure was applied.
 416 Orthogonal projection, a common debiasing technique in machine learning and NLP, was
 417 applied to remove the stylistic bias introduced by the academic writing conventions shared
 418 across all texts. An empty document following the input structure was encoded by *SPECTER2*,

⁴ <https://github.com/allenai/SPECTER2/issues/14>

419 producing a vector that captures this generic style rather than any specific content. Each
420 document vector was then projected onto the orthogonal complement of this baseline, so that
421 the resulting representation reflects thematic content alone.

422
423 Then, cosine similarity was computed between each publication vector and each call vector.
424 The resulting per-publication scores were then aggregated into a single researcher-level score
425 for each publication set. The aggregation rule was determined heuristically through iterative
426 testing, inspecting cases where extreme values introduced noise or where overly restrictive
427 thresholds excluded relevant profiles. The final rule applies the arithmetic mean when the
428 publication set contains few works, and switches to the mean over the top 33% of publications
429 by similarity score when the set is sufficiently large. Specifically, if the top 33% of a
430 researcher's publications in a given set amounts to two papers or fewer (less than 7 publication
431 records), the arithmetic mean over the full set is used instead; otherwise, the top 33% mean is
432 applied. This prevents individual highly aligned but isolated works from disproportionately
433 inflating the score of researchers whose overall output is not genuinely close to the call.

434
435 Prior to aggregation, each researcher's similarity scores were normalised within their own
436 distribution, rescaling individual scores relative to each researcher's profile rather than across
437 the full population. The aggregated and normalised scores were then used to compute percentile
438 ranks across the full institutional population for each call and publication set. For the purposes
439 of this analysis, researchers at or above the 95th percentile were treated as strong candidates,
440 as this threshold identifies the top 5% of the community by alignment with a given call.

441 442 **3.3. Data and code availability**

443 All scripts were developed in *R* and *Python*. *R* was used for database construction, including
444 *Scopus* data retrieval, bibliometric processing and indicator construction. *Python* handled the
445 embedding and similarity pipeline, covering vectorisation and cosine similarity computation,
446 with the sentence-transformers library providing the *SPECTER2* implementation. The
447 embedding model was executed on *Google Colaboratory*. All scripts are fully replicable and
448 openly available at GitHub (<https://github.com/claraaortega/Paper-Call-Project>).

449 450 **4. Results**

451 The results are presented in two complementary analyses. The first examines how researcher
452 assignments are distributed across calls and indicators, assessing whether recommendations
453 spread broadly or concentrate on a few individuals, and whether the four indicators provide
454 overlapping or distinct outputs. The second explores a specific case in depth to provide a
455 qualitative validation of the recommendations produced.

456 457 **4.1. Assignment distribution and indicator complementarity**

458 Of the UGR researchers identified in *Scopus*, 2,662 (88%) appear in at least one of the 291
459 calls with an assignment under at least one indicator (**Table 4**). Coverage is broad, yet it varies
460 considerably across indicators. *Research background* produces the highest number of
461 assignments (2,540 researchers), whilst *Current leadership*, which applies the most selective
462 criteria, covers 1,432. Each indicator also captures researchers that the others miss. *Research*
463 *background* returns 297 unique researchers not identified by any other indicator, *Research*
464 *leadership* adds 55, and *Current focus* contributes 24. *Current leadership* adds no exclusive
465 assignments, meaning that every researcher it identifies is also captured by at least one other
466 indicator. Across all indicators combined, researchers receive an average of 20.1 unique call
467 recommendations. Around half (1,281) receive recommendations under all four indicators,
468 whilst 376 (14%) appear under only one.

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Table 4. Assignment summary by indicator

	Researchers	Unique researchers	Average call per researcher	Average researcher per call
<i>Research background</i>	2,540	297	14.6	128.0
<i>Current focus</i>	2,004	24	14.6	101.2
<i>Research leadership</i>	1,883	55	14.6	95.0
<i>Current leadership</i>	1,432	0	14.7	72.4
Total	2,662	---	20.1	184.3

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Figure 2 shows the distribution of recommended calls per researcher for each indicator. All four distributions are right-skewed and strikingly similar in shape, with a median of 13 calls per researcher and comparable interquartile ranges. This similarity, however, does not imply redundancy. It is a direct consequence of the shared design logic. Each indicator applies the same 95th percentile threshold independently for every call, which mechanically generates a comparable number of assignments per call regardless of the indicator used. The average number of recommended calls per researcher is therefore approximately 14 for each indicator individually, rising to 20.1 when unique calls across all indicators are combined. In other words, the distributions look alike because the selection mechanism is structurally identical, not because the indicators recommend the same people.

Figure 2. Distribution of recommended calls per researcher for each indicator. Left panels show histograms; the right panel displays the corresponding box plots.

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To assess whether the indicators identify the same researchers and rank them similarly, assignment overlap and percentile rank correlation were examined jointly (**Table 5**). Overlap values range from 37% to 75%, and Spearman rank correlations between 0.55 and 0.71, confirming that no two indicators are interchangeable. The clearest distinction runs between the general indicators (*Research background* and *Current focus*) and the leadership-based ones (*Research leadership* and *Current leadership*). Within each group, assignments and rankings

493 are more consistent, but, across groups, both overlap and correlation drop noticeably, with
 494 cross-pair values reaching as low as 37% and $\rho = 0.55$. The asymmetry in overlap values is
 495 also informative. Leadership indicators tends to show higher overlap into the general ones (65-
 496 75%), but this reflects a size effect rather than redundancy. Because leadership indicators
 497 produce fewer assignments, a larger share of their pairs naturally satisfies the less restrictive
 498 thresholds of the general indicators. The reverse direction confirms this interpretation. Only
 499 37-56% of general-indicator pairs also appear in the leadership indicators, indicating that the
 500 broader indicators capture a substantial set of researchers whom the leadership criteria exclude.

501

502 **Table 5.** Pairwise overlap between indicators, expressed as the percentage of call-researcher
 503 pairs in the row indicator also present in the column indicator, and the Spearman correlation
 504 between the percentile ranks assigned by each indicator pair.

Call-researcher pairs and percentile correlation in row indicator (%) also present in column indicator	<i>Research background</i>	<i>Current focus</i>	<i>Research leadership</i>	<i>Current leadership</i>
<i>Research background</i>		58% $\rho=0.69$	56% $\rho=0.71$	37% $\rho=0.56$
<i>Current focus</i>	74% $\rho=0.69$		51% $\rho=0.55$	53% $\rho=0.67$
<i>Research leadership</i>	75% $\rho=0.71$	54% $\rho=0.55$		50% $\rho=0.64$
<i>Current leadership</i>	65% $\rho=0.56$	74% $\rho=0.67$	66% $\rho=0.64$	

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507 **4.2. Case study**

508 To assess whether the framework produces meaningful recommendations in practice, **Table**
 509 **6** presents the two highest-ranked calls for a researcher affiliated with the Department of
 510 Criminal Law at UGR, whose work centres on criminal law and criminology, with particular
 511 emphasis on cybercrime and the protection of fundamental rights. In recent years, this
 512 researcher's output has increasingly engaged with artificial intelligence and big data, mirroring
 513 a broader trend across the social sciences and humanities. Across all four indicators, the
 514 framework recommends a total of 38 unique calls for this researcher. **Table 6** focuses on the
 515 two highest-ranked calls per indicator to illustrate how the prioritisation shifts depending on
 516 the dimension considered. Seven of the eight entries belong to *Horizon Europe* Cluster 3 (civil
 517 security for society) and address border security, customs and supply chain integrity, organised
 518 crime prevention and operational cybersecurity. The exception is a Cluster 2 call (culture,
 519 creativity and inclusive society) on advisory support to counter disinformation and foreign
 520 information manipulation and interference (FIMI), which explicitly targets the application of
 521 AI and big data to detect and debunk disinformation. All eight entries are thematically coherent
 522 with the researcher's documented expertise, and none can be dismissed as a false positive or an
 523 artefact of the matching process.

524

525 Most of these calls appear across multiple indicators, yet the ranking they receive differs
 526 substantially. The call on customs and supply chain security (HORIZON-CL3-2025-01-BM-
 527 03), for instance, features in three of the four top-two lists but occupies a different position in

528 each, reflecting how each indicator weighs the researcher's profile differently. Under *Current*
529 *leadership*, it is ranked first with a percentile of 100, meaning that the researcher's recent
530 leading-author output is the most closely aligned in the entire institutional population. More
531 revealing is the behaviour of *Current focus*, which is the only indicator to place the FIMI call
532 among the top two, ranking it in first position (2nd rank, 99.95th percentile). This result directly
533 captures the researcher's recent pivot towards AI-related topics. Because *Current focus*
534 operates on a two-year window, it is sensitive to thematic shifts that the five-year indicators
535 inevitably dilute. Had the framework relied solely on *Research background*, this highly
536 relevant call would not have appeared among the top recommendations. Conversely, *Research*
537 *leadership* uniquely surfaces the call on organised crime intelligence (HORIZON-CL3-2025-
538 01-FCT-03) in its top two, reflecting the researcher's longer-standing expertise as a leading
539 author in that area. The case confirms that the four indicators, rather than merely expanding
540 coverage, reshape the priority order in ways that carry practical significance for the researcher.
541

542 **Table 6.** Top-two recommended calls per indicator for the selected researcher.

Indicator	Call	Rank	Percentile
<i>Research background</i>	HORIZON-CL3-2025-01-BM-02 Open topic on secured and facilitated crossing of external borders	2 nd	99.96
	HORIZON-CL3-2025-01-BM-03 Open topic on better customs and supply chain security	2 nd	99.96
<i>Current focus</i>	HORIZON-CL2-2025-01-DEMOCRACY-01 Advisory support and network to counter disinformation and foreign information manipulation and interference (FIMI)	2 nd	99.95
	HORIZON-CL3-2025-01-BM-03 Open topic on better customs and supply chain security.	5 th	99.80
<i>Research leadership</i>	HORIZON-CL3-2025-01-FCT-03 Open topic on improved intelligence picture and enhanced prevention, detection and deterrence of various forms of organised crime	2 nd	99.95
	HORIZON-CL3-2025-02-CS-ECCC-02 New advanced tools and processes for Operational Cybersecurity	2 nd	99.95
<i>Current leadership</i>	HORIZON-CL3-2025-01-BM-03 Open topic on better customs and supply chain security	1 st	100
	HORIZON-CL3-2025-02-CS-ECCC-02 New advanced tools and processes for Operational Cybersecurity	1 st	100

543

544 **5. Discussion**

545 This work presents the first grant recommendation framework that combines bibliometric
546 profiling with semantic matching in a reproducible and scalable architecture. Previous systems
547 have been designed for specific funding agencies and disciplinary domains. Zhu et al. (2023)
548 built a BERT-based classifier trained on *NIH* publication-grant pairs, whilst Z. Zhang et al.
549 (2024) employed biomedical word embeddings over the same ecosystem. Both produce
550 effective recommendations within their scope, but their architectures are tightly coupled to
551 *PubMed* and *NIH* data, requiring retraining to operate elsewhere. The present framework
552 separates the methodological logic from its data instantiation, so that any combination of
553 bibliographic source, embedding model and funding programme can be plugged in without
554 reengineering the pipeline. The case study, applied to the University of Granada and 291

555 *Horizon Europe* topics, shows that recommendations reach a broad share of the research
556 community rather than concentrating on a few dominant profiles.

557
558 A second contribution is the multidimensional profiling strategy. Prior approaches represent
559 researchers either through a single aggregated profile (Z. Zhang et al., 2024) or through
560 unsupervised thematic clusters (Zhu et al., 2023), yielding one recommendation list per
561 researcher. The present framework constructs multiple publication sets per researcher, each
562 defined by a distinct bibliometric criterion, and compares each independently against the call.
563 The resulting indicators distinguish consolidated expertise from recent activity, and leading
564 contributions from peripheral ones. This granularity is particularly relevant for research offices,
565 which need to assess not only thematic proximity but also the nature of a candidate's
566 engagement with a topic.

567
568 The within-researcher normalisation deserves specific attention. By standardising similarity
569 scores relative to each researcher's own distribution, the system penalises thematically
570 dispersed profiles and rewards concentrated ones. An important consequence is that scores are
571 recalculated with every new call, making the framework inherently dynamic. Rankings shift as
572 both the researcher's output and the available calls evolve, so no score accumulates over time,
573 that is, each ranking reflects alignment with a specific opportunity at a specific moment. The
574 same individual may therefore rank very differently depending on the moment, but this
575 variability captures the reality that relevance is always relative to the funding opportunity at
576 hand.

577
578 The framework also opens practical avenues beyond individual recommendation. By cross-
579 referencing indicators, it becomes possible to detect complementarities within the institution,
580 pairing a senior researcher with strong background alignment with an early-career colleague
581 who scores well on current leadership, or identifying profiles from different departments that
582 together cover the scope of a multidisciplinary call. Although this capability is not formalised
583 in the present implementation, the underlying data structure supports it. Similarly, the fixed
584 thresholds used in the case study could be replaced by adjustable controls in an institutional
585 deployment, allowing research officers to modify parameters and recalculate rankings
586 interactively.

587 588 **5.1. Limitations**

589 The principal methodological limitation is the absence of a ground truth dataset. Prior work
590 has exploited retrospective *NIH* data linking funded outputs to specific calls at the researcher
591 level (Z. Zhang et al., 2024; Zhu et al., 2023), sometimes complemented by expert ratings (Z.
592 Zhang et al., 2024). *Horizon Europe* publishes funded project data through *CORDIS*, but only
593 at the institutional level, without identifying which researcher led a given proposal. An
594 alternative strategy based on publication acknowledgements is equally problematic, since the
595 relationship between a researcher's bibliometric record and the calls they actually pursued is
596 mediated by consortium composition, strategic decisions and institutional politics, none of
597 which bibliometric data capture. Moreover, the multi-indicator design complicates quantitative
598 benchmarking, as a researcher may rank differently depending on the time window or
599 publication set considered. This is a deliberate choice rather than a shortcoming. Each indicator
600 carries a distinct interpretive logic, and the traceability of individual publications behind each
601 score supports informed human judgement rather than replacing it.

602
603 The reliance on *Scopus* in the case study limits the representativeness of the humanities and
604 social sciences, whose output is often published through more local and specific channels. The

605 framework itself is not bound to *Scopus*, and an institution seeking broader coverage could
606 substitute or complement it with other sources as described in Section 2.1.1.

607
608 Some calls are inherently interdisciplinary, drawing on vocabularies that rarely co-occur in a
609 single publication record. No individual researcher is likely to achieve high alignment with
610 such calls unless their profile already bridges the relevant domains. The framework mitigates
611 this through its multi-indicator structure, which can reveal partial alignments that a single score
612 would obscure, but it does not fully resolve the challenge.

613
614 Finally, the percentile-based ranking introduces a structural tension. The system always
615 identifies a top 5% for every call, even when no researcher has a meaningful thematic
616 connection, potentially overstating the quality of the best available match. Conversely, for calls
617 with many strongly aligned researchers, relevant candidates may fall just below the threshold.
618 Users should therefore interpret percentile positions as relative standings within the
619 institutional community rather than as absolute measures of suitability.

620

621 **6. Final remarks**

622 This paper has presented a reproducible framework for matching researchers to funding calls
623 through the combination of bibliometric profiling with semantic matching. Unlike previous
624 systems, which are bound to specific funding agencies and domains, the proposed approach
625 separates the methodological logic from its data instantiation, allowing any bibliographic
626 source, embedding model or funding programme to be integrated without re-engineering the
627 pipeline. The case study confirms the practical viability of the approach, with the four
628 indicators producing complementary rather than redundant recommendations, and qualitative
629 inspection validating the coherence of individual profiles. The framework is conceived as an
630 institutional tool that positions each researcher within their own community, supporting
631 research offices in the strategic allocation of expertise to funding opportunities. Its reliance on
632 openly available models and standard bibliometric data keeps computational costs low and
633 makes the approach scalable to institutions of varying size and disciplinary breadth. Future
634 work should focus on constructing ground-truth benchmarks for formal evaluation, extending
635 the system to detect complementarities between researchers for multidisciplinary calls, and
636 integrating it into an interactive platform for operational deployment.

637

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